

PREPARATION OF Pt-Fe ALLOY NANOPARTICLES BY ELECTRICAL WIRE EXPLOSION PROCESS

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the Fe-Cr-Al particle surface, were produced in liquid media.

1 Introduction

The ease of preparing homogeneous mixtures, suspensions, and slurries makes weakly aggregated nanopowders very attractive for powder technologies. Various techniques have been developed to prepare metal nanopowders, such as gas-phase chemical reaction [1], spray pyrolysis [2], laser ablation [3], flame processing [4], and vapor deposition [5]. Among the many techniques used to fabricate nanocrystalline powders, electrical wire explosion (EWE) is a promising method for producing a number of materials with new properties [6]. By applying a large impulse current, a thin metal or alloy wire in certain gas and/or liquid media can explode. It is known that nanometer sized particles can be obtained by the EWE method, when it was conducted in liquid media. This method is particularly advantageous to produce nanoparticles in high yield and shorter reaction time [7].

The Fe-Cr-Al alloys have outstanding stability compared to other iron-based alloys at high temperatures and have been used in the fabrication of catalyst support, gas burners, industrial heaters, and other high-temperature devices [8,9]. Platinum is an expensive active metal in diesel oxidation catalysts for internal combustion engines [10] and there is a need to explore possible opportunities to reduce the Pt content in catalyst systems for economic reasons. There has been a great deal of research activity to develop novel catalysts with high catalytic activity and thermal stability, including core-shell and bimetallic nanocatalysts [11,12,13].

In this paper, we present the synthesis of Pt-Fe alloy nanoparticles by the EWE method. The Pt-Fe alloy nanoparticles, where Pt nanoparticles are attached at

2 Experimental Section

2.1. Syntheses of Pt-Fe Alloy Nanoparticles

Pt-Fe alloy nanoparticles were synthesized by the EWE method (Scheme. 1.) in ethyl alcohol media using commercial Pt and Fe-Cr-Al wire as source materials. In the EWE method, a metal wire was installed between high-voltage electrodes, which were connected to a capacitor bank of 60 μF through a triggered spark gap switch. The wires were continuously fed by a feeding roller installed on the exploding vessel and were guided by a nozzle into the vessel. A voltage of 2.0 kV was applied to the metal wire. The metal wire was overheated and evaporated swiftly when a very strong pulse current with current density $2.9 \times 10^8 \text{ A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ passed through the wire, resulting in an explosion. The expansion duration could be as short as several tens of microseconds [14-16]. Fe-Cr-Al wires with a diameter of 0.1 mm were first exploded and subsequently condensed in ethyl alcohol media. Then, Pt wires with a diameter of 0.1 mm were exploded and subsequently condensed in the Fe-Cr-Al colloidal solution to produce Pt-Fe nanoparticles.

2.2. Characterization

The crystal structure of the Pt-Fe nanoparticles made by the EWE method was analyzed using an X-ray diffractometer (XRD; D-Max 2200, RIGAKU, JPN). The morphologies and compositions of the Pt-Fe nanoparticles were characterized by transmission electron microscopy, energy dispersive spectroscopy (TEM; JEM-2100F, JEOL, JPN), scanning electron microscopy (SEM; JSM-6700F, JEOL, JPN) and X-

ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS; Sigma Probe, Thermo VG Scientific equipped with an Al-K α X-ray source (1486.3 eV)).

Scheme. 1. Synthesis of Pt-Fe alloy nanoparticles by the EWE method.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1. Synthesis of Pt-Fe nanoparticles

Fig. 1. shows the X-ray diffraction patterns of the Pt-Fe nanoparticles formed by the EWE method under ethyl alcohol media. The diffraction patterns of Pt-Fe nanoparticles show peaks corresponding to Pt, Fe and Fe-Cr-Al alloy. The Fe peaks could be due to Fe-Cr-Al colloids, as metal vapors segregate during explosion of the Fe-Cr-Al wire.

Fig. 1. X-ray diffraction pattern of Pt-Fe alloy nanoparticles.

3.2. Morphologies of Pt-Fe nanoparticles

Fe-Cr-Al wires were exploded and condensed in ethyl alcohol media. Then, Pt wires were exploded and subsequently condensed in the Fe-Cr-Al colloidal solution to produce Pt-Fe nanoparticles. Generally, the wire was overheated and evaporated swiftly when a very strong pulse current with high current density passed through it, resulting in explosions that produced a shock wave, forming metal powders. Unless a complete evaporation of the metal wire occurs due to an insufficient supply of energy in the EWE process, the wire was split into the metal vapors and the overheated metal droplets [17,18]. The overheated metal droplets formed by incomplete evaporation of the wire would be changed to submicro- and micrometer sized particles.

Fig. 2. shows the particle size distribution of Pt-Fe particles formed by the EWE method under ethyl alcohol media. The average size of the Pt-Fe alloy nanoparticles is ~120 nm; however some micron-size particles were also formed.

Fig. 2. Particle size distribution of Pt-Fe alloy nanoparticles.

Fig. 3. shows the morphologies of the Pt-Fe micro-particles prepared by the EWE method. The prepared micro-particles are almost spherical in shape and several micrometer in size. The energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) results show that each element (Pt, Fe, Cr) was uniformly dispersed on the particles regardless of particle size.

Fig. 3. SEM EDS images of Pt-Fe micro-particles produced by the EWE method.

On the other hand, if complete evaporation of the wire occurs during the EWE process, the number of these coarse particles significantly decreases and the number of nanometer-sized particles increases. As shown in Fig. 4, the prepared particles are about several tens of nm in size, indicating that complete evaporation occurred in this Pt-Fe nanoparticle preparation using the EWE process. The EDS results again show that each element (Pt, Fe, Cr) was uniformly dispersed on the nano-size particles.

Fig. 4. TEM EDS images of Pt-Fe nanoparticles produced by the EWE method.

These alloy nanoparticles showed very good dispersion stability more than 7 days in ethyl alcohol media without surfactant. In addition, the size of the particles was uniform regardless of the explosion time.

3.3 X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy

XPS measurements reveal chemical composition and oxidation states of Pt, Cr and Fe on Pt-Fe-alloy particles.

Fig. 5. XPS of Fe-Cr-Pt alloy nanoparticles (a) Pt4f (b) Fe2p and (c) Cr2p.

Fig. 5. shows the X-ray photoelectron spectra of Fe-Cr-Pt alloy nanoparticles after calcination at 600°C in air/30 min. Surface analysis of the Fe-Cr-Pt nanoparticles shows peaks corresponding to all of the constituent elements [19]. Fig. 5. (a) reveals XPS peaks corresponding to Pt4f. A deconvoluted spectrum shows the presence of the main peak ($f_{7/2}$) at 71.2, 72.2 and 74.1 eV, which can be assigned to Pt⁰ (58 %), Pt⁺² (13.5 %) and Pt⁺⁴ (28.4 %), respectively [19,20]. Fig. 5. (b) shows photoemission spectrum of the Fe2p main peak ($p_{3/2}$) with a binding energy value of 707.0 and 709.1 eV, indicating the presence of metallic Fe (62 %) and Fe⁺² (38%). These BEs observed for Fe 2p_{3/2} are in good agreement with those previously reported [17]. Fig. 5. (c) shows XPS of Cr2p with BE values of the main peak ($p_{3/2}$) at 574.4 and 576.9 eV [19,20]. These binding energies can be attributed to Cr⁰ (52.4%) and Cr⁺³ (47.6 %). Formation of surface oxides of the constituent metals could be due to surface oxidation during the electrical explosion and calcination step.

Table. 1. Surface composition of Fe-Cr-Pt alloy

XPS peaks	Pt4f	Fe2p	Cr2p	O1s	C1s
Surface composition	0.044	0.070	0.032	0.290	0.563

Table. 1. shows surface composition of Fe-Cr-Pt alloy particles after considering XPS sensitivity factors. The surface of the alloy nanoparticles is enriched with a considerable amount of carbon which results from the organic solvent (ethanol in this study). Apart from carbon, the surface is enriched by Fe or Pt, suggesting that Pt-Fe alloy particles can be good catalytic materials for Pt or Fe based catalysis such as diesel oxidation or ammonia synthesis.

4 Conclusions

Nanocrystalline Pt-Fe alloy particles of different sizes with an average size of ~120 nm and uniform spherical shape were formed by wire electrical explosion. Each element (Pt, Fe, Cr) was uniformly dispersed on the particles regardless of particle size. The colloidal particles were highly stable in an ethanolic solution over more than a week. These hybrid nanoparticles synthesized by electrical explosion could be used as catalysts for reactions like diesel oxidation for CO and hydrocarbon oxidation.

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